

AEUE - International Journal of Electronics and Communications

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--Manuscript Draft--

Manuscript Number:	
Article Type:	Research paper
Keywords:	Bulk-Driven; Ultra Low-Voltage; Ultra Low-Power; Rail-to-Rail; Comparator
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A Novel Ultra Low-Voltage / Low-Power Rail-to-Rail Comparator Topology in Nanoscale CMOS Technology

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Abstract

The article addresses a novel topology of analog voltage comparator capable of processing the input voltage in rail-to-rail range. We propose two different innovative comparator topologies. One topology is employing a standard “gate-driven” (GD) control of MOS transistors and designed in 65 nm CMOS technology. The other one, designed in 130 nm CMOS technology, uses rather unconventional “bulk-driven” (BD) control of active devices in the circuit. Each presented circuit topology has its own pros and cons, however both are suitable and actually aimed for ultra low-voltage (ULV) and/or ultra low-power (ULP) applications. The proposed comparator designs have been extensively analyzed for robustness and parameter stability across all fabrication process corners, a wide temperature range (from -20 °C to 85 °C), and for random process variations, as well. Both presented comparator designs can reliably operate with power consumption in nano-watt range without any fuse trimming or calibration, as the proof of concept has been confirmed by measurements performed on prototype chips.

Key words: Bulk-Driven, Ultra Low-Voltage, Ultra Low-Power, Rail-to-Rail, Comparator

1. Introduction

The analog voltage comparator, as a circuit building block, has been around for decades, and its application field is very wide. However, the onset of battery-powered electronic devices and overall shift to green energy

sources (e. g. energy harvesting) motivates the circuit designers to look for innovative solutions to lowering the overall power consumption of electronic systems integrated on a chip. In such applications, the required silicon area might not be the most important parameter anymore [1]. The emerging technologies such as 3 nm GAAFET or 1 nm nano-sheet FET technology nodes are focused on high-performance digital Systems-on-Chip (SoC), as they exhibit unparalleled power efficiency per area in digital circuits [2, 3]. Nevertheless, the cost per wafer, variability of the process parameters, gradual loss of deterministic behavior of transistors, ESD and thermal issues, electro-migration and many other effects are the reasons why mixed-signal and analog integrated circuits (IC) are still being designed in mature bulk CMOS processes such as 130 nm and higher (very often much higher). Pure analog design in such technology nodes is next to impossible without complex calibration and/or expensive post-process trimming.

Analog voltage comparator, a prime example of mixed-signal circuit, usually contains a device pair at the input in order to obtain the differential signal from the input voltages, which is then processed further towards generating the digital output signal carrying the decision information. The differential pair by itself, however, cannot process the whole span of the input voltage due to its limitations in terms of common-mode range. In order to obtain rail-to-rail range of processed input voltage, the comparator topology has to contain additional circuitry. There have been developed several solutions, each with its own pros and cons, as well a field of application [4–13]. The conventional approach would be to employ two differential pairs with both transistor types. Although, this topology ensures rail-to-rail input range, it also requires a biasing circuitry, usually with a start-up block, as well. This kind of input circuitry can be designed for ULP applications with appropriate transistor dimensions, but three stacked transistors increase the minimal required power supply voltage. ULV conditions (below 0.6 V) for any kind of integrated circuit usually require special approach to topology design and it also often forces IC designers to use a non-standard fabrication technology (e. g. PD/FD-SOI or floating-gate CMOS [10]), which increase the total cost.

The motivation for our work lies within the aforementioned reasons. We are proposing a novel, “silicon-proven” analog voltage comparator topology suitable for both ULP as well as ULV applications, which can be designed in standard (nowadays low-cost) bulk CMOS technology without the need for calibration circuitry and/or trimming process. Since the comparator might

be implemented in ULV system, its input voltage range has to be rail-to-rail, in order to obtain a necessary voltage headroom. The proposed topology does not require a biasing block that simplifies and speeds-up the design period and also reduces the overall power consumption. The transistor sizing can be automated using g_m/I_D methodology [14]. Naturally, a lowered current (drawn from the power supply) limits the dynamic behavior for a given capacitance load, which can be viewed as obligatory drawback of ULV and ULP electronic circuits.

The article is organized as follows. The following section contains an overview of state-of-the-art in the area of analog voltage comparator design. Section 3 represents a comprehensive description of the proposed circuit topology in high detail. Section 4 discusses the results of laboratory measurements on prototype chips and post-layout simulations, which prove the correct behavior of the proposed designs in various conditions. It also presents a comparison with relevant state-of-the-art works. The final section concludes the paper.

2. State-of-the-Art of ULP/ULV Comparators

The current state-of-the-art comparator designs are being designed in nanoscale CMOS technologies (180 nm and lower), where the traditional design solutions, as well as novel circuit topologies are becoming difficult to realize even for experienced IC designers and the choice of such fabrication process poses a challenge all on its own. The presented overview of state-of-the-art comparators discussed in section represents a summary of recent publications (not older than 4 years, as of 2022) with focus on ULV and/or ULP designs preferably with input rail-to-rail capability. This research is meant to combine current trends in comparator design and to discuss the properties of proposed topologies.

The authors of [15] published a two-stage comparator in 90 nm CMOS technology implemented in an analog-to-digital converter (ADC) design. The comparator is capable of working with 4 GHz signal at $V_{DD} = 0.8$ V with propagation delay in pico-seconds, which seems really promising. However, there is no information about loading capacitance. The problem is that the paper does not contain information about the design's input offset voltage, nor does it discuss its robustness under process and temperature variations. Furthermore, judging by the topology, it should not be able to work in rail-to-rail range, hence one should consider this publication as a basic concept.

Very interesting solution can be found in [16]. The authors present a fully synthesizable comparator with rail-to-rail input range, capable of correct operation with $V_{DD} = 0.3$ V and $P_{DD} = 10$ nW, which is truly an astonishing result. Thanks to its digital nature, the silicon area consumption is also remarkably low. The main disadvantage of the published research is high input offset voltage. One can also expect high variation of all analog parameters, as standard cells are built with the minimum channel length that technology can provide. This publication is the only one with reported loading capacitance.

In [17], a comprehensive design with thick oxide devices working with $V_{DD} = 3.3$ V, is presented. The overall concept including rail-to-rail feature and reported parameters seem very promising, and the power consumption within the micro-watt range is reported. The authors do not discuss the biasing block in the paper and 130 nm process was used for presented topology.

Another fully synthesizable analog comparator is reported in [18]. The researchers used 180 nm process and the proposed design is also fabricated and measured, which is great reference point. It is built with just a couple of standard cells and is well suited for Internet of Things (IoT) with the minimum supply voltage down to the value of 0.15 V, and power consumption in pico-watts. Again, the downside is expected high variation of all electric parameters such as increased input offset voltage. However, the power consumption and silicon area requirements are unparalleled.

In [19], the authors propose another synthesizable comparator based on standard cells. This design uses 16 nm process node employing FinFET transistors with $V_{DD} = 0.7$ V. As a contrast to the previous digital comparator designs, this topology employs 3-input NOR gates rather than NAND gates. The proposed comparator exhibits power consumption in units of micro-watts across a wide temperature range. The paper does not include information about the offset voltage or Mont-Carlo analysis results. Again, one should consider the presented analog comparator as a basic concept.

Based on the presented state-of-the-art designs, we can conclude that the ULV / ULP analog comparators designed in nanoscale technologies based on analog topology tend to consume up to tens of micro-watts, while the designs relying on standard cells provide excellent power and silicon area efficiency for the price of accuracy and parameter instability with regards to process and temperature variations.

3. The proposed ULV/ULP comparator topology

The proposed comparator topology works in so-called *current-mode*, as it converts the input voltage into a current flow proportionally. The difference signal is generated by cross-coupled transistors from both sides of the differential structure. The initial research working with nominal $V_{DD} = 0.6$ V and “silicon-proven” proof of concept was published in [20], discussing the design in high detail. Our novel comparator designs combine high accuracy, rail-to-rail input range, ultra low-power consumption, ultra low-voltage capability and low dependence on process variations. The price for this is increased silicon area needed to layout the design. With a low drain current flowing through the respective MOS transistors (biased into *weak inversion* conditions) the devices are becoming rather large (large W.L product), in order to limit the drain current, but also keep a reasonable transconductance. Increased W.L area, on the other hand, greatly improves the robustness against process variations and mismatch between devices, if laid out correctly. Let us first describe the BD topology designed and fabricated in 130 nm CMOS technology. This design is more suitable for low-voltage applications, since the maximum supply voltage is limited by latch-up effect. The second proposed topology is a classic “gate-driven” GD circuit capable of both low-power, as well as low-voltage operation, designed in 65 nm CMOS technology.

3.1. Bulk-Driven ULV Comparator

The transistor-level schematic diagram is depicted in Fig. 1. The detailed description can be found in [20]. The proposed re-design of cited work is set to work with $V_{DD} = 0.4$ V as the nominal supply voltage, the added programmable hysteresis can be also asymmetric and the measurements on prototype silicon chips have confirmed hypothesis about the minimum value of supply voltage for given topology. We successfully demonstrated a correct operation with $V_{DD} = 0.25$ V. We also added to the original topology an “enable” function, so the power consumption can be set to leakage level, while the circuit’s operation is not required. It can also mimic the “clocked” dynamic comparator behavior.

The transistors M_{in+} and M_{in-} act as current source controlled by the input voltage. The current is then mirrored by devices $M1 - M3$ and $M6 - M8$. The difference voltage is generated in $diff$ and \overline{diff} nodes by NMOS current mirrors formed by $M4 - M5$ and $M9 - M10$. The pull-up devices M_{PU} and pull-down device M_{PD} ensure stable, known and non-floating potential while

Figure 1: The proposed analog core of bulk-driven rail-to-rail comparator.

in shut-down mode. Transistors M_h introduce the current disbalance in the circuit when activated by logic zero at their gate terminal, enabling identical biasing conditions as the main input transistor. The amount of hysteresis and its polarity is set just by the device sizing and activation.

3.2. Gate-Driven ULP Comparator

A novel GD comparator topology designed in 65 nm CMOS technology, based on the one previously described, is shown in Fig. 2. The main function remains same as before, since its reliable operation has been successfully demonstrated on prototype chip samples. However, the current source is composed by gate-driven cross-coupled transistors of both types. This introduces a rail-to-rail range for the input voltage, and also removes the risk of triggering the latch-up effect. This in turn increases the safe operational voltage up to the nominal levels within chosen technology. The enable function requires an extra transmission-gates, which either connects the respective transistors into a diode within the current mirror, or disconnects the gates of mirroring transistors from the diode, while the circuit's operation is being inhibited.

Figure 2: The proposed analog core of gate-driven rail-to-rail comparator topology.

The device sizing determines the level of inversion and therefore, the current drawn by the circuit. This is the reason why transistors in the input current source part are rather large. The effect of increased channel length is two-fold. Firstly, it limits the current flow through the whole circuit and secondly, it greatly improves its stability against process variations, which are significant in 65 nm technology.

The output stage used in both presented comparators is depicted in Fig. 3. In both cases, we implemented a classic latch circuit in order to improve noise margin of the circuit. The output inverter is sized according to load capacitance and slew rate requirements. The control digital circuit has been designed at RTL and synthesized with emphasis on power consumption.

(a) Output latch of the bulk-driven comparator.

(b) Output latch of the gate-driven comparator.

Figure 3: Output stages along with the controlling logic blocks.

Buffers processing the difference signal are custom-designed push-pull amplifiers with a digital inverter at their outputs. The local feedback comprised of sensing the digital output signal prevents the circuit from cross-conduction in the latch. This situation has been observed when the power supply voltage is rippled or unstable over time. The input 2-bit code (Fig. 3a) is processed by the control block, which in turn generates a logic signal for the respective transistors responsible for introducing the hysteresis in decision-making.

3.3. Small-Signal Analysis

The small-signal analysis needs to be carried out for both comparator designs separately due to differences in topologies. Thanks to a complete symmetry of the bulk-driven version, we can analyze just a half of the circuit.

The left-hand side of the small-signal model can be seen in Fig. 4. The detailed analysis along with the analytical definition of voltage amplification can be found in [20].

Figure 4: Small-signal model of left-hand side of the bulk-driven analog core.

A complete small-signal model of gate-driven comparator topology can be found in Fig. 5. In this case, we cannot benefit from the circuit symmetry due to the cross-coupled input branches.

Figure 5: Complete small-signal model of gate-driven analog core.

The definition of voltage amplification is written in Eq. (1). The formula represents only an approximate relying on “reasonable” analog design with output conduction of transistors being several orders of magnitude smaller than their transconductance. Naturally, the formula is valid only when all devices are saturated.

$$A_{V_{diff}} \approx \frac{\left[\frac{g_{m3} \cdot g_{mMNin+}}{g_{m1}} + \frac{g_{m9} \cdot g_{m7} \cdot g_{mMPin-}}{g_{m10} \cdot (g_{mMPin-} - g_{m8})} \right]}{g_{ds3} + g_{ds9}} \quad (1)$$

3.4. Physical Design

The quality of physical design is of utmost importance when dealing with ULV and/or ULP circuits. Usage of nanoscale CMOS technology by itself

introduces a number of complications. However, with correct layout design techniques, we can mitigate most of possible lithography and process variations, as well as thermal gradients present on silicon die. Layout designs of both presented comparators are depicted in Fig. 6 along with the total dimensions.

(a) Layout of the BD comparator in 130 nm technology.

(b) Layout of the GD comparator in 65 nm technology.

Figure 6: Physical layout designs of the proposed rail-to-rail comparators.

Our physical design contains advanced transistor matching techniques, dummy structures, full guard rings of both types and enlarged N-well areas in order to minimize the well-proximity effect. These measures, on the other hand, increased the silicon area requirements roughly by 15 %.

4. Measurement and Post-Layout Simulation Results

The prototype chips fabricated in 130 nm technology has been extensively tested by laboratory measurements at room temperature. The experimental results have been compared to post-layout simulations and compiled together in this section of the paper. The gate-driven topology designed in 65 nm CMOS technology has been verified by post-layout simulations in various working condition,s and the achieved results are presented alongside with its BD counterpart.

4.1. DC sweep

Arguably, the most basic parameter of any voltage comparator is its transfer characteristics (DC response) with a constant reference voltage. The measured and simulated results of such a test are depicted in Fig. 7. In order to prove the rail-to-rail feature, the reference voltage value was set only a few mV from the power supply and ground rails, as well as to the very center of the voltage range.

(a) DC characteristics of bulk-driven comparator. (b) DC characteristics of gate-driven comparator.

Figure 7: Comparator transfer characteristics for various reference voltages.

Regarding the BD comparator, we also verified the functionality of its programmable hysteresis. Fig. 8a shows the results of all four possible levels of hysteresis defined by 2-bit input code. One can observe that the level of hysteresis is not binary-weighted, which proves our previous statement about possible fully-customizable shape of the presented curve. Fig. 8b displays the results of current consumption measurement with V_{REF} set to the center of the voltage range, for ten different chip samples. As one can observe, the shape of the measured curves is identical with reasonable dispersion due to fabrication process variations. The disagreement between the simulation and experimental results after the output toggle is caused by the threshold voltage model inaccuracy present in the provided PDK. Moreover, the measured current consumption includes the leakage current drawn by six ESD structures and PCB parasitics, which in our case can represent up to 30 % of the overall consumption. In an on-chip application without the ESDs and PCB, the expected power consumption is significantly lower.

Figure 8: Additional parameters of BD comparator with reference voltage at half of V_{DD} .

4.2. Input Offset Voltage

One of crucial parameters of any voltage comparator is its input offset voltage, which is in direct relation with its decision accuracy. In ideal state, the comparator would have zero offset between the input signals. However, due to real-world imperfections such as process and lithography variations, the input voltage can cause significant problems when neglected during circuit design. Furthermore, the parameter variations are increasing with smaller feature size on silicon die. In other words, the devices in nanoscale CMOS technologies exhibit substantial dispersion when compared to processes above $1 \mu\text{m}$. To tackle this, one can use post-processing trimming, additional calibration circuitry or large devices within the circuit itself. Each of mentioned approached has its own pros and cons.

We have chosen the third option to minimize the input offset voltage of the proposed comparator designs. The offset voltage value has been simulated for both comparator designs by means of Monte-Carlo analysis. We used a slow triangle voltage and a constant reference voltage in the center and close to the supply rails. In this way, we obtained the offset value for both output edges. The described analysis was repeated for ambient and corner temperatures as well as three different reference voltages. Hence, Monte-Carlo simulations provided together 3000 and 1800 individual values for bulk-driven and gate-driven topologies, respectively. As one can observe, the mean value in both cases remains around 1 mV, the standard deviation is less than 3 mV.

(a) Simulation results of bulk-driven comparator for various temperatures and reference voltages. (b) Simulation results of gate-driven comparator for various temperatures and reference voltages.

Figure 9: Monte-Carlo analysis of the input offset voltage.

4.3. Power Consumption

The most important parameter from ULP/ULV applications point of view is the power consumption in various operating conditions. As mentioned before, the BD topology has been designed for nominal $V_{DD} = 0.4$ V, while the GD version uses the nominal supply voltage value of chosen CMOS technology, which in our case is $V_{DD} = 1.2$ V. Since the comparator topology works in current-mode, the overall current draw depends on the input voltage. The bulk-driven comparator was measured with three different values of the reference voltage at ambient temperature. Results achieved for the discussed experiment are displayed in Fig.10a. As stated earlier, the measured power consumption includes the PCB parasitics and reverse current consumed by ESD structures. The gate-driven counterpart has undergone a set of Monte-Carlo simulations in the worst-case voltage conditions. The simulation results in form of a histogram for ambient and both corner temperatures are depicted in Fig. 10b. Surprisingly, the highest power consumption is observed at low operating temperature. However, from 500 obtained samples, the highest power consumption value is less than 850 nW, while in the nominal voltage and temperature conditions, the power consumption remains safely in the first third of nano-watt range.

In order to verify the hypothesis about the minimum supply voltage value for given schematic (stated in [20]), we also carried out the functional and power analysis with lowered V_{DD} for the BD version. The waveforms shown in Fig. 11 display results with the supply voltage values of 350 mV, 300 mV

(a) Measured power consumption of bulk-driven comparator for various reference voltages. (b) Worst-case power consumption of gate-driven comparator for various reference voltages.

Figure 10: Power analysis of the proposed comparator topologies.

and 250 mV, respectively. The picture also contains dotted lines denoting the reference level for each measurement. Results for power consumption $P_{DD} = 350$ mV are satisfactory, as the offset voltage remains negligible and the consumption is proven to be below $1 \mu\text{W}$ with the voltage reference set to the range center. The power consumption lowers accordingly with the supply values of 300 mV and 250 mV, however, the offset voltage rises to 81.3 mV and 72.5 mV, respectively. These values represent 27 % and 29 % of the voltage range.

Figure 11: Measured power consumption of the BD comparator with lowered supply voltage.

Again, we need to keep in mind that the observed power consumption also includes the laboratory setup and ESD leakage, as well. In further defense of these results, the proposed topology was not designed for such a low V_{DD} , yet it still works with lowered quality of accuracy. Hence, we believe it is safe to claim that with accurate simulation models, one can design and realize the proposed topology deep inside the weak inversion (V_{DD} between 200 and 250 mV, probably with narrower temperature range). Such a research is included in our future plans.

4.4. Dynamic Parameters

Naturally, with ULV and/or ULP working conditions, one can expect very limited maximum frequency and overall dynamics. Moreover, the current flow (and slew rate) within the analog core depends on the input voltage conditions. We investigated both output edges separately, while we swept the overdrive voltage (voltage exceeding a fixed reference level), and while we swept the reference voltage with fixed overdrive level as well. Fig. 12 depicts the measured and simulated results of the first experiment with the BD comparator.

(a) Rising output edge delay as a function of the overdrive voltage.

(b) Falling output edge delay as a function of overdrive voltage.

Figure 12: Dynamic properties of BD comparator as a function of overdrive voltage.

The results for the second analysis with BD comparator are shown in Fig. 13. To our surprise, the loading capacitance of ESDs, oscilloscope probe and PCB parasitics added up to 36 pF, which is several times higher than our design expected. Both output edges would exhibit lower propagation delay in an on-chip application. The detailed analysis of dynamic behavior, as well

as simulation of on-chip application was published in [21]. We can still report a good correlation in the presented waveforms.

(a) Rising output edge delay as a function of the reference voltage.

(b) Falling output edge delay as a function of the reference voltage.

Figure 13: Dynamic properties of BD comparator as a function of the reference voltage.

The gate-driven design was investigated by the same set of transient analyses but naturally in broader voltage range and with load of $C_{LOAD} = 200$ fF modeling rather higher on-chip load. The simulation results for the nominal process and temperature conditions are shown in the following figures. Since the current source of the GD comparator consists of two MOS devices in parallel, one should expect rather interesting behavior. Fig. 14 depicts the analysis with swept overdrive voltage. The resulting curves are similar to their BD counterparts in terms of shape.

(a) Rising output edge delay as a function of the overdrive voltage.

(b) Falling output edge delay as a function of the overdrive voltage.

Figure 14: Dynamic properties of the GD comparator as a function of the overdrive voltage.

The results of swept reference with given constant overdrive voltage are depicted in Fig. 15. The propagation delay peaks for the minimum value of the overdrive voltage is up to $480 \mu\text{s}$, which corresponds to frequency slightly higher than 2 kHz. However, with more reasonable overdrive voltage, the maximum frequency shifts upwards considerably.

Figure 15: Dynamic properties of GD comparator as a function of the reference voltage.

4.5. Comparison and Discussion

All important parameters of the proposed comparator designs are neatly summarized in Tab. 1 along with the state-of-the-art works and their publication year. As for comparison with two other GD comparators, our design performs better in terms of power consumption and simulation verification depth. Although, work published in [18] is superior in *measured* P_{DD} and required silicon area, our BD comparator design exhibits great accuracy, robustness over process variations and programmable, customizable hysteresis. Our GD design also uses the most advanced technology out of all non-synthesizable circuits.

Table 1: Overall comparison of proposed designs with state-of-the-art publications

	Technology	V_{DD} (V)	P_{DD}	f_{max} (MHz)	Topology	Rail-to-Rail	Hysteresis	Verification
Our work	130/65 nm	0.4/1.2	1.7*/0.18 μW	0.16-2.5 / 0.05-3	BD/GD	2x Yes	Programmable / No	Measured / PVT
[15] (2018)	90 nm	0.8	8.42 μW	4 000	GD	No	No	Typical Sim.
[16] (2020)	65 nm	0.3	10 nW	10	Digital	No	No	Typical Sim.
[17] (2021)	130 nm	3.3	37 μW	7.3	GD	Yes	Programmable	Monte-Carlo
[18] (2021)	180 nm	0.15	10 pW	0.0023	Digital	Yes	No	Measured
[19] (2022)	16 nm	0.75	3.6 μW	-	Digital	Yes	No	Typical Sim.

* Including ESD and PCB parasitics

5. Conclusion

We presented a comprehensive scientific work focused on ULV and ULP integrated voltage comparator design in 130 nm (with $V_{DD} = 0.4$ V) and 65 nm (with $V_{DD} = 1.2$ V) CMOS technologies. The BD re-design fabricated in 130 nm process demonstrates and confirms the relevance of our work and also opens the door for further investigation of V_{DD} reduction as our prototype circuit demonstrated functionality with $V_{DD} = 0.25$ V at ambient temperature. This observation favors our hypothesis about the minimal V_{DD} . The overall measured parameters correlate well with the post-layout simulation results. The GD version designed in 65 nm process (also based on our previous work) has been verified by means of Monte-Carlo and corner simulations in the industrial temperature range. Both comparator topologies can safely operate in nano-watt range as of their power consumption. The designs will occupy the silicon area depending on the input offset voltage specifications but the topology can be easily modified for trimmed devices as well. The rail-to-rail and programmable hysteresis features have been successfully confirmed on a prototype chip too. So in the closing, we do believe, both novel comparator topologies presented in this paper are a fair portion of scientific work, supported by solid researched theoretical background and confirmed by hard data.

Our future plans include an optimized BD design for V_{DD} below 250 mV, an implementation of programmable hysteresis into the GD topology, laboratory measurements on fabricated prototype chip samples, and last but not least, employ the proposed comparator in a ADC design and calibration circuitry. All of the above would be done in 65 nm CMOS technology.

Acknowledgments

This work was supported in part by the Slovak Research and Development Agency under grant APVV-19-0392 and the Scientific Grant Agency under grant VEGA 1/0760/21. This work has also received funding from the Electronic Components and Systems for European Leadership Joint Undertaking under grant agreement No. 876868. This Joint Undertaking receives support from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme and Germany, Slovakia, Netherlands, Spain, Italy.

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Declaration of interests

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests:

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We the undersigned declare that the manuscript entitled "**A Novel Ultra Low-Voltage / Low-Power Rail-to-Rail Comparator Topology in Nanoscale CMOS Technology**" is original, has not been full or partly published before, and is not currently being considered for publication elsewhere.

We confirm that the manuscript has been read and approved by all named authors and that there are no other persons who satisfied the criteria for authorship but are not listed. We further confirm that the order of authors listed in the manuscript has been approved by the undersigned.

We understand that the Corresponding Author is the sole contact for the editorial process. The corresponding author "**Lukas Nagy**" is responsible for communicating with the other authors about process, submissions of revisions, and final approval of proofs."

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4. Jan. 2023